

The electronic properties of three popular high spin complexes $[M(\text{acac})_3]$, $M = \text{Cr}$, Mn , and Fe revisited: an experimental and theoretical study.[†]

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The occupied and unoccupied electronic structure of three high spin $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_3$ ($\text{TM} = \text{Cr}$, Mn , and Fe) complexes has been studied by revisiting their literature vapour-phase He(I) and He(II) (when available) photoemission (PE) spectra and by means of original near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) spectroscopic data recorded at the O K-edge (^oK-edge) and TM L_{2,3}-edges (TML_{2,3}-edges). The assignments of the vapour-phase He(I)/He(II) PE spectra have been guided by the results of spin-unrestricted non-relativistic Slater transition state calculations, while the ^oK-edge and TML_{2,3}-edges spectroscopic evidences have been analysed by exploiting the results of spin-unrestricted scalar-relativistic time-dependent density functional theory (DFT) and DFT/ROCIS calculations, respectively. Despite the actual symmetry (D_3 , in the absence of any Jahn-Teller distortions) of title molecules allows an extensive mixing between TM t_{2g}-like and e_g-like atomic orbitals, the use of the Nalewajski–Mrozek TM–O bond multiplicity index combined to a thorough analysis of the ground state (GS) outcomes allowed the assessment of the TM–O bond weakening associated to the progressive TM 3d-based e_g-like orbitals filling. The experimental information provided by ^oK-edge spectra was rather poor; nevertheless, the combined use of symmetry, orbitals and spectra allowed us: i) to rationalise minor differences characterizing spectral features along the series; ii) to quantify the contribution provided by the ligand-to-metal-charge-transfer (LMCT) excitations to the different spectral features; iii) to recognize the t_{2g}/e_g-like nature of the TM 3d-based orbitals involved in LMCT transitions. As far as the TML_{2,3}-edges spectra and the DFT/ROCIS results are concerned, lowest lying TML_{2,3} spectral features include states having either the GS spin multiplicity ($S(\text{I}) = 3/2$, $S(\text{II}) = 2$) or, at higher excitation energies (EEs), states with $\Delta S = \pm 1$. At variance to that, only states with $\Delta S = 0, -1$ significantly contribute to the TML_{2,3} spectral pattern. Along the whole series, the L₂ higher EE side is systematically characterized by states involving TM2p → π₄ MLCT excitations. As such, coupled-single excitations with $\Delta S = 0$ are involved in I and II, while single MLCT 2p → π₄ transitions with $\Delta S = -1$ are involved in III.

1. Introduction

The pentane-2,4-dione, commonly addressed as acetylacetonate, is the simplest member of the β-diketone compounds and the precursor of one of the most prominent and versatile ligand (L) in coordination chemistry: the bidentate, negatively charged, acetylacetonate (acac).¹ Acac may bind to transition metal (TM) ions in different ways;² nevertheless, the bidentate chelating form, with both O atoms bound to TM to generate a six-membered pseudoaromatic ring,³ is by far the most common.^{2,4} $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_n$ complexes usually imply $n = 2$ or $n = 3$, with $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_2$ quite often oligomeric, to allow the TM coordinative saturation, and $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_3$ characterized by an octahedral arrangement of the six O atoms around TM (see Figure 1).⁵⁻⁶ Among $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_3$, the peculiar properties of the high spin (HS) $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$, $\text{Mn}(\text{acac})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ (I, II, and III, respectively) make them interesting for both basic and applied research.⁷⁻⁹ More specifically, besides its *marial* uses,¹⁰ the deep maroon I is extensively

used as a precursor in the plasma assisted Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD)^{9a} and as a dopant agent in sol-gel silica films.^{9b} Moreover, in the last few years, it has been employed as a general precursor for the synthesis of early TM oxide nanomaterials and nanoparticles¹¹⁻¹² as well as redox species of redox flow batteries.¹³⁻¹⁶ Furthermore, its high degree of photostability makes it the prototype Cr^{III} complex for ultrafast time-resolved spectroscopic studies.¹⁷

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_3$. The central violet sphere corresponds to the TM^{III} ion (Cr^{III} in I, Mn^{II} in II, and Fe^{III} in III), while red, grey, and white spheres represent oxygen, carbon, and hydrogen atoms, respectively. In the adopted framework, z and C₃ axes coincide.

As far as the dark black-brown II is concerned, it has been the object of several theoretical^{8d,18} and experimental^{18c,19} studies, which ultimately demonstrated the Mn^{II} octahedral local environment^{19a,b} as well as its HS state.^{7,19c} Moreover, its effectiveness as a radical initiator and a hydroperoxide decomposition catalyst has been exploited in the autoxidation

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[†] Electronic supplementary information (ESI) available: Tables S1 – S3: DFT-BP86 optimized coordinates of title molecules; Fig. S1: Spin-unrestricted scalar relativistic ZORA TD-DFT 1st excitation spectra of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ evaluated with diverse exchange-correlations functionals: SAOP, LB94, PBE0 and M06; Fig. S2: Extended ^oK-edge NEXAFS spectra of I, II and III.

of ethyl linoleate, a model compound for the binder molecule in household alkyd paint.²⁰ The last TM(acac)₃ herein considered, the bright red HS **III**,⁷⁻⁸ is widely employed in industry as a catalyst, in particular in the organic chemistry with alkenes²¹ and polyurethane.²² Additionally, it has been also found effective in catalytic processes such as the polymerization of 1,3-benzoxazine,²³ the dimerization of isoprene to 1,5-dimethyl-1,5-cyclooctadiene and 2,5-dimethyl-1,5-cyclooctadiene,²⁴ and the formation of 1,3-oxazolidine products.²⁵ More recently, **III** has been also exploited as precursor for nanoparticles' syntheses,²⁶ while an electrolyte based on the neutral/negatively charged (-1) **III** has been recently developed for p-type dye-sensitized solar cells.²⁷

Despite the very large amount of literature concerning title compounds, a comparative assessment of their TM-L bonding scheme by taking advantage of peculiarities such as i) the same *octahedral* coordinative environment of the TM ion, ii) the same oxidation number of the TM ion, iii) the same number of TMt_{2g}-like electrons,^{5,7} and iv) the progressive increasing of the TMe_g-like electron number,^{5,7} is still lacking. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that not only a definitive assignment of the vapour-phase UV photoemission (PE) spectra of **I** – **III**²⁸ is still missing, but the same relative energy ordering of corresponding ground state (GS) occupied frontier molecular orbitals (MOs)^{8h,29-31} deserves to be reconsidered.

Near edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) spectroscopy is unanimously recognized as a tool able to probe, site-selectively, the empty frontier MOs, the TM coordinative environment, as well as the nature and the strength of the TM-L bonding in TM complexes.³²⁻³⁵ In the recent past, we thoroughly investigated the nature, the localization and the relative position of frontier MOs of three TM(acac)₂ complexes, namely [Co(acac)₂],⁴⁸ [Mn(acac)₂],⁴⁸ and [Cu(acac)₂],⁴⁹ by modelling their TML_{2,3}-edges spectra³⁶ either by employing the current Restricted Open Shell Configuration Interaction with Singles (DFT/ROKIS) method⁵⁰ ([Co(acac)₂] and [Mn(acac)₂]) or by means of time dependent (TD) density functional theory (DFT) calculations⁵¹ within the Tamm-Dancoff approximation⁵² coupled to the relativistic zeroth-order regular approximation (ZORA)⁵³ including spin-orbit coupling (SOC) effects ([Cu(acac)₂]). The main aim of these studies was that of looking into the role played by the TM electronic configuration, the TM coordinative geometry, and the TM-L symmetry restricted covalency⁴⁷ in determining the TML_{2,3} spectral patterns. ^OK-edge, TML_{2,3}-edges data and theoretical results herein reported complement experimental^{17,29} and theoretical outcomes^{8c-8h,54} appeared in the literature in the last few years about title compound shedding, at the same time, new light into the TM-L bonding scheme and suggesting an alternative assignment of the lowest ionization energy (IE) region of their literature vapour-phase He(I) PE spectra.

2. Computational and Experimental Details

2.1. Geometry optimizations. Geometrical parameters of **I**, **II** and **III** have been optimized by using the Amsterdam Density

Functional (ADF) suite of programs (version 2014.01).⁵⁵ Numerical experiments have been carried out by running spin-unrestricted non-relativistic (NR) DFT calculations with generalized gradient corrections self-consistently included through the Becke-Perdew formula⁵⁶ and by adopting a triple- ζ with a polarization function (TZP) Slater-type basis set for all the atoms. Moreover, the 1s – 2p TM AOs as well as the 1s AO of C and O atoms have been kept frozen throughout the calculations. The geometry optimization of **I** and **III** has been carried out by assuming a D₃ symmetry,^{5,57} while no symmetry constraint has been assumed for **II**. As a matter of fact, X-ray crystallographic data pertaining to **II** are consistent with the presence of two crystal structures (β and γ), the former characterized by a moderate (0.05 Å) tetragonal compression,^{19a} the latter typified by a significant tetragonal lengthening (0.2 Å).^{19bc} In this regard, Krzystek *et al.*,^{19c} on the basis of their EPR measurements, suggested that the elongated γ structure is the natural form of the Jahn-Teller distortion for the *octahedral* HS 3d⁴ Mn ions, while the compressed β one could be a consequence of undetermined crystal packing effects. In passing, theoretical calculations confirmed the stabilizing effect associated to the Jahn-Teller elongation or predicted a stable elongated structure.¹⁸ According to that and independently of the starting geometry we assumed (tetragonally elongated or compressed), the optimized structure of **II** systematically converged toward the same elongated arrangement. More specifically, the observed Jahn-Teller tetragonal distortion generating four short (hereafter, (Mn–O)^s) and two long (hereafter, (Mn–O)^l) bonds with average bond lengths of 1.935 and 2.111 Å, respectively,¹⁹ has been quantitatively reproduced independently of the starting geometry. Independently of all this, to facilitate the comparative assessment of the TM-L bonding and to assign ^OK-edge and L_{2,3}-edges features as seamless as possible, the electronic properties of title molecules will be discussed within the assumption of a D₃ symmetry and by taking advantage of the TM local *octahedral* environment.^{5,7} Additional information about the localization and the bonding/antibonding character of selected MOs over a broad range of energies has been gained by exploiting partial density of states (PDOS) and the overlap population DOS (often referred to as crystal orbital overlap population – COOP).⁵⁹ Corresponding plots, based on the Mulliken's prescription for partitioning the overlap density,⁶⁰ have been obtained by applying a 0.25 eV Lorentzian broadening factor. Finally, the Ziegler transition state (²TS) scheme⁶¹ has been used to gain further insights into the nature of the TM-L interaction.

2.2. K-edge NEXAFS calculations. ^OK-edge NEXAFS spectra of **I**, **II** and **III** have been modelled by evaluating excitation energies (*E*E) and corresponding oscillator strengths (*f*) for transitions having the linear combinations of 1s^O AOs as initial spin orbitals (isos).⁶² To this end, all-electron spin-unrestricted scalar relativistic (SR) TD-DFT ZORA calculations⁶³ suitably tailored to treat deep core excitations,⁶⁴ have been run. SR TD-DFT ZORA numerical experiments have been carried out by

adopting all-electron quadruple- ζ plus four polarization functions (QZ4P) ZORA basis sets for all the atoms;⁶⁵ moreover, to adequately describe transitions towards high energy virtual MOs and Rydberg states,⁶⁴ QZ4P ZORA sets of symmetry-related atoms specifically involved in the excitation processes have been further augmented with two shells of diffuse functions accordingly to the even tempered criterion. The adiabatic local density approximation has been employed to approximate the exchange-correlation (XC) kernel,⁶⁶ while diverse functionals (PBE0,⁶⁷ SAOP,⁶⁸ LB94,⁶⁹ and M06⁷⁰) have been preliminarily tested on I to approximate the XC potential in the self-consistent field calculations. The best agreement between theory and experiment has been provided by the PBE0 functional (f distributions evaluated with PBE0,⁶⁷ SAOP,⁶⁸ LB94⁶⁹ and M06⁷⁰ XC functionals are compared with the ^{10}K -edge spectrum of I in Fig. S1 of the ESI $\ddagger$); ^{11}f and ^{13}f distributions have been then obtained by considering only the PBE0⁶⁷ XC functional. Scaled ZORA orbital energies instead of the ZORA orbital energies in the TD-DFT equations have been employed to improve deep core EEs .^{64c-64e,64g,72}

2.3. $L_{2,3}$ -edge NEXAFS calculations. $L_{2,3}$ -edges spectra of I, II and III have been modelled by evaluating EEs and corresponding f for transitions having the $^{TM}2p$ -based MOs as isos. To this end, the ORCA program package⁵⁰ has been exploited. More specifically, $L_{2,3}$ -edges $^{V/III}f(EE)$ distributions have been evaluated by means of the DFT/ROCIS method,^{42c,42g} by adopting the hybrid-DFT PBE0 XC functional and the def2-TZVP(-f) basis set.⁷³⁻⁷⁵ As a consequence of the strong 2p SOC in the final state manifold, excited states (ESs) with S^7 different from the GS one had to be considered. The combined use of DFT and CI needs a set of three semi-empirical parameters (c_1 , c_2 , c_3); we adopted the following values for them: $c_1 = 0.21$, $c_2 = 0.49$, and $c_3 = 0.29$.^{42c} Throughout the calculations, the resolution of the identity approximation⁷⁶ has been used with the def2-TZVP/J basis set^{73b} (a detailed description of basis sets' acronyms is reported in the ORCA manual: <https://orcaforum.cec.mpg.de/>). Finally, the ZORA has been adopted to treat SR effects. Numerical integrations have been carried out on a dense Lebedev grid (302 points).⁷⁷ Simulated spectra of I, II and III have been shifted by 3.2, 10.0 and 10.3 eV, respectively, to superimpose the highest intensity feature of the experimental and simulated L_3 -edge, which does not suffer from the extra broadening and the distortion due to the Coster-Kronig Auger decay process.^{42j,78} Incidentally, this is needed because absolute theoretical EEs carry errors arising from DF deficiencies in the core region, one-particle basis set restrictions and inadequacies in the modelling of spin-free relativistic effects.^{42b} A Gaussian broadening factor of 1.0, 1.8 and 1.2 eV has been applied to model $L_{2,3}$ -edge NEXAFS spectra of I, II and III, respectively.

2.4. Experimental spectra details. Synchrotron radiation NEXAFS measurements were performed at the CNR-IOM beamline ALOISA (Elettra Synchrotron, Trieste).⁷⁹ Molecular films were deposited on gold coated thin glass wafers by thermal evaporation from a homemade crucible of boron nitride in an ultra-high-vacuum environment (base pressure of

10^{-10} mbar during measurements). Title complexes have been evaporated at about the same temperature of ~ 350 K, eventually reaching a max pressure of $3 - 5 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar during evaporation. Along the deposition, we kept the substrate at $T_S \sim 220$ K, in order to reduce the surface mobility for enhancing dendritic 2D growth, while preventing the sticking of water molecules from the residual gas (whose condensation on Au takes place below 200 K). Finally, we obtained films of ~ 2.2 , ~ 3.2 and >6 nm for Fe-, Cr- and Mn- (acac)₃ compounds respectively, as estimated from the attenuation of the substrate Au 4f photoemission signal. NEXAFS spectra have been measured keeping the sample at grazing angle of 6° , while orienting the surface to the magic angle for the incoming linearly polarized X-ray beam. NEXAFS measurements have been performed in partial electron yield by means of a full aperture channeltron placed along the surface normal. The employed channeltron is additionally equipped with a repeller grid in front of it, which is negatively biased to reject secondary electrons and let in the Auger electrons corresponding to the relevant electronic transitions. In particular, we polarized the grid at the voltage of -490 and -550 V for the O 1s and Cr 2p ionization thresholds, respectively. Absolute calibration of the photon energy was obtained for the O 1s and Cr 2p thresholds by simultaneously recording of the drain current on the last mirror of the beamline after the exit slits. The last mirror presents a gold film on top of a Cr and Fe coating, which absorption lines are measurable and used as a reference for the metallic L_3 main peak: Cr at 574.1 eV.⁸⁰ Absolute calibration of the O 1s ionization threshold was also obtained by the K-edge absorption line in the drain current due to oxygen contamination (mostly CO) on the surface of the last mirror. This absorption feature was previously calibrated by simultaneously measuring the vibrational structure of the O K-edge threshold from CO gas (central peak at 534.21 eV) thanks to a windowless, differentially pumped, in-line gas ionization cell.⁸²

2.5. Synthesis details. Title compounds have been prepared as previously reported⁸³ and purified by means of three recrystallization steps. Compounds purity was confirmed by elemental analysis (EA). IEA, C₁₅H₂₁CrO₆: calculated C 51.57 %, H 6.06 %; found: C 51.62%, H 6.08%. IIEA, C₁₅H₂₁MnO₆: calculated C 51.14%, H 6.01%; found: C 51.13%, H 5.98%. IIIEA, C₁₅H₂₁FeO₆: calculated C 51.01%, H 5.99%; found: C 51.03%, H 6.00%.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Occupied Electronic Structure. The forthcoming discussion may take advantage of a preliminary qualitative description of title molecules' frontier orbitals⁸⁴ simply based on symmetry arguments and overlap considerations. Frontier MOs of a single C_{2v} acac fragment may be split in two sets according to their σ or π character.⁸⁵ The former set consists of two completely occupied fragment MOs (FMOs): the in-phase (n_+) and the out-of-phase (n_-) linear combinations of the O lone-pairs, both of them lying in the acac plane. As far as the latter

set is concerned, it consists of five FMOs (π_1 , π_2 and π_3 DOMOs and π_4 and π_5 VMOs),³¹ all of them perpendicular to the acac plane. Moreover, π_j FMOs are symmetric or anti-symmetric with respect to the reflection plane perpendicular to the molecular one and passing through the methinic carbon atom (C(H)) if j is odd (π_o) or even (π_e) (see Figure 4 of the ref. 85), respectively. Finally, as far as the bonding nature of π_4 and π_5 VMOs is concerned, they are both C–O antibonding and mainly localized on the C atoms; additionally, the π_4 VMO has a node on the C(H) atom, while the π_5 one is also C–C(H) antibonding. When three acac fragments are coordinated about TM to generate a regular D_3 TM(acac)₃ complex (see Fig. 1),⁵ linear combinations of $n_{+/-}$ and π_e FMOs will transform as the D_3 $a_1 + e$ irreducible representations (IRs), while those generated by n_{-} and π_o FMOs will transform as the D_3 $a_2 + e$ IRs. Incidentally, literature data pertaining to the free acac fragment indicate that topmost occupied FMOs ($n_{+/-}$, n_{-} and π_3) have the following energy ordering: $E_{\pi_3} > E_{n_{+/-}} > E_{n_{-}}$.⁸⁵

As far as the central TM^{III} ion is concerned, its *octahedral* environment lifts the five-fold orbital degeneracy of the TM 3d AOs generating three t_{2g} -like orbitals ($a_1 + e$ in the actual D_3 symmetry of **I** and **III**, and hereafter labelled as ${}^a t_{2g}$ and ${}^e t_{2g}$, respectively)^{5,86} and two e_g -like MOs (e in the actual D_3 symmetry of **I** and **III**).^{5,86} Accordingly, the HS TM^{III} electronic

configuration will be $a_1^2 e^2 e^0$ (GS = ${}^4 A_2$) in **I**, $a_1^3 e^2 e^1$ (GS = ${}^5 E$) in **II** and $a_1^2 e^2 e^2$ (${}^6 A_1$) in **III**.⁸⁷ The $O_h \rightarrow D_3$ descending symmetry allows then us to foresee: i) an extensive mixing among linear combinations of $n_{+/-}$ and $\pi_{e/o}$ acac-based FMOs of e symmetry; ii) the interaction of these linear combinations with both ${}^e t_{2g}$ and e_g -like TM^{III} 3d based orbitals;⁸⁶ iii) the unfeasibility of a net distinction between σ and π contributions to the TM–L bonding. Moreover, the relative energy position of frontier acac-based FMOs⁸⁵ lets us to predict that the TM–L bonding should be dominated by the interaction between the e TM 3d AOs and the linear combinations of the acac-based $n_{+/-}$ and π_3 FMOs of the same symmetry.⁸⁶ Finally, the HS nature of **I**, **II**, and **III** further allows us to expect that: i) the overall interaction between the spin $\uparrow$ components of the $n_{+/-}$ and π_3 FMOs and the TM t_{2g} -like 3d AOs will be weakly antibonding in nature for the whole series; ii) the overall interaction between the spin $\uparrow$ components of $n_{+/-}$ and π_3 FMOs and the TM e_g -like 3d AOs will gradually weaken the TM–O bonding upon moving from **I** to **III**.

Such a qualitative picture perfectly matches ADF GS results as demonstrated by the inspection of Figs. 2 and 3 where the TM 3d PDOS and the spin $\uparrow$ COOPs between M^{III} 3d AOs and $n_{+/-}$ and π_3 FMOs are displayed, respectively.

Fig. 2 TM 3d PDOS of the valence states of **I**, **II**, and **III**. Vertical bars correspond to the HOMO (solid lines) and LUMO (dashed lines) energy. Contribution from ${}^a t_{2g}$ (z^2 , dotted curves) and ${}^e t_{2g}$ (xy and $x^2 - y^2$, dashed curves) PDOS are also displayed.

The first thing to be noted is the different nature and/or localization of the HOMO and LUMO in the three complexes. According to Liu and Conradie,^{29b} the topmost occupied MOs of **I** (the closely spaced $30e(\uparrow)$ 1 HOMO and the $18a_1(\uparrow)$ 1 HOMO-1, see Fig. 2)⁸⁸ correspond to the Cr^{III} ${}^e t_{2g}(\uparrow)$ and ${}^a t_{2g}(\uparrow)$ orbitals strongly mixed with the Cr^{III} e_g -like ones. As suggested on a qualitative ground, the $18a_1(\uparrow)$ MO is almost completely localized on the Cr 3d z^2 AO (78%), while the ${}^e t_{2g}$ and the e_g -like sets similarly contribute (40% and 27%, respectively) to the 1 HOMO, which accounts for a Cr–O antibonding interaction

between ${}^e t_{2g}/e_g$ -like Cr^{III} AOs and the e combinations of the acac-based π_3 FMO (see Figs. 3 and 4). As a whole, the Cr–O bonding picture emerging from the BP86 results is consistent with a quite extensive mixing between the Cr^{III} 3d AOs and the (acac)₃³⁻-based FMOs; nevertheless, the inspection of Fig. 3 ultimately testifies that the TM–L bonding is dominated by the interaction between the e linear combination of the (acac)₃³⁻-based $n_{+/-}$ FMOs and the empty Cr^{III} e_g -like 3d AOs.⁸⁹ Useful insights into this matter can be further obtained by referring to Fig. 5 where spin $\uparrow$ and spin $\downarrow$ COOPs between the TM^{III} e_g -like

3d AOs and the e linear combination of the $(\text{acac})_3^{3-}$ -based n_- and n_+ FMOs are displayed. COOP curves make well evident that, according to Pritchard and Autschbach,⁹⁰ both the spin $\uparrow$ and the spin $\downarrow$ component of the $(\text{acac})_3^{3-}$ -based n_- FMOs concur to the dative $L \rightarrow \text{Cr}^{\text{III}}$ bonding, while the n_+ contribution is negligible for both spins. Incidentally, data reported in Figs. 2, 3 and 5 allow the identification of the orbital (the 28e DOMO)⁹¹ accounting for the most relevant contribution to the Cr–O bonding (the participation of the Cr^{III}

e_g -like AOs⁸⁶ to the 28e($\uparrow$) orbital amounts to 8%). As a whole, the Cr–O COOPs reported in Figs. 3 and 5 combined to the Cr–O Nalewajski–Mrozek⁹² bond multiplicity index ($I^{\text{NM}} = 0.47$)⁹³ and the comparison of Cr/O Hirshfeld(Q_{Hir})⁹⁴/Voronoi(Q_{Vor})⁹⁵ gross atomic charges (see Table 1) with those consistently computed for the isostructural $\text{Al}(\text{acac})_3$ ⁹⁶ complex concur to stress the leading role played by the ionic contribution in the Cr–O bonding.

Fig. 3 Spin $\uparrow$ COOPs between TM^{III} t_{2g} -like (dotted lines)/ e_g -like (solid lines) 3d AOs and $(\text{acac})_3^{3-}$ FMOs in I, II and III. Bonding (antibonding) combinations correspond to positive (negative) peaks in the COOP plot. Vertical bars represent the HOMO energy.

As far as the ${}^a t_{2g}$ $18a_1(\downarrow)$ 1 LUMO is concerned (see Figs. 2 and 4), it is of some relevance to underline that, differently from the ${}^a t_{2g}$ $18a_1(\uparrow)$ 1 HOMO-1 partner, the L participation (64%) involves the a_1 combination of the acac-based π_4 FMO (see Fig. 4). As expected, a last look at the left panel of Fig. 2 confirms the presence, among low lying VMOs and rather close to the 1 LUMO ($\Delta E \sim 1$ eV), of the Cr^{III} -based e_g -like⁸⁶ orbitals (the 32e($\uparrow$) VMOs) strongly mixed, as expected, with the ${}^e t_{2g}$ ones.

It is well known that information about the details of the occupied frontier MOs of volatile compounds may be gained by exploiting the vapour-phase UV PE spectroscopy.⁹⁷ He(I) PE spectra of title compounds have been firstly recorded early in the '70s by Evans *et al.*,^{28a} and even though Van Dam and Oskam,^{28b} the Vovna research group^{28c,28f} and Westmore *et al.*^{28e} tackled the same problem in the following years, a definitive assignment of title molecules' He(I) lowest lying PE spectral features (*vide infra*), is not yet assessed.

Fig. 4 3D plots of one component of the 30e($\uparrow$) 1 HOMO and of the $18a_1(\downarrow)$ 1 LUMO. Displayed isosurfaces correspond to ± 0.05 $e^{1/2} \text{Å}^{-3/2}$ values.

Fig. 5 Spin $\uparrow$ and spin $\downarrow$ COOPs between TM^{III} e_g -like 3d AOs and the e linear combination of the $(\text{acac})_3^{3-}$ -based n_- (solid lines) and n_+ (dotted lines) FMOs.

Bonding (antibonding) combinations correspond to positive (negative) peaks in the COOP plots. Vertical bars represent the HOMO energies.

In this regard and before anything else, it has to be underlined that: i) He(I) ¹PE spectra reported by Akopyan *et al.*,^{28c} Westmore *et al.*,^{28e} and by Vovna *et al.*^{28f} are all consistent with the He(I) ¹PE spectrum firstly recorded by Evans *et al.*,^{28a,98,99} ii) the whole He(I) ¹PE spectral pattern is only present in the ref. 28f, but its resolution is very poor; iii) the He(I) ³PE spectrum recorded by Evans *et al.*^{28a} is very similar to that collected by Westmore *et al.*^{28e} but significantly different from those published for the same molecule by Akopyan *et al.*^{28c} and by Vovna *et al.*^{28f}. In particular, neither the British^{28a} nor the Canadian^{28e} research group revealed any PE feature between 9.22 and 10.16 eV; at variance to that, the He(I) spectra published by the Vovna group^{28c,28f} are both characterized by the presence of a peak that Akopyan *et al.*^{28c} placed at 9.64 eV. Finally, similarly to **II**, an extremely weak ³PE feature seems to characterize the lowest IE region of the ³He(I) PE spectrum recorded by Vovna *et al.*^{28f}

Table 1 Nalewajski–Mrozek⁹² TM–O bond multiplicity index (I^{NM}), Hirshfeld⁹⁴ (Q_{Hir}^{TM}) and Voronoi⁹⁵ (Q_{Vor}^{TM}) charges of TM and O atomic species, and bonding energies (BEs in kcal/mol) of **I**, **II** and **III** decomposed according to the ⁵TS scheme⁶¹ and taking **I** as a reference.

	I	II	III
I^{NM}	0.47	0.25/0.46 ^a	0.38
$Q_{Hir}^{TM}/Q_{Vor}^{TM}$	0.58/0.55	0.37/0.26	0.43/0.35
Q_{Hir}^O/Q_{Vor}^O	-0.21/-0.22	0.21/-0.20 ^b 0.17/-0.16 ^c	-0.19/-0.19
BE	0	27	61
ΔE_{ster}	0	-17	-115
ΔE_{int}	0	44	176

^aThe former (latter) value refers to the (Mn–O)¹ ((Mn–O)²) bonds. ^bValues relative to the O atoms involved in the two (Mn–O)¹ bonds. ^cValues relative to the O atoms involved in the four (Mn–O)² bonds

Van Dam and Oskam^{28b} assigned “without any doubt” the lowest lying peak Y (7.46 eV) of the He(I) ¹PE spectrum to the ionization from “metal d-orbitals” by exploiting their relative intensity variations upon switching from the He(I) to the He(II) ionizing source (see Fig. 2 of the ref. 28b).¹⁰¹ Actually, in the habit of the Gelius model,¹⁰² the photoionization cross-section σ_i of the i^{th} MO is

$$\sigma_i = \sum_{v, nt} c_{nt, v}^i \sigma_{nt}^v \quad (1)$$

where $(n\ell)$ sums over the states localized on the atomic centres v and contributing to the i^{th} MO, σ_{nt}^v corresponds to the atomic subshell photoionization cross-section (ASPCS), and the $c_{nt, v}^i$ coefficients account for the MO occupancy. According to Berndtsson *et al.*,¹⁰³ the $c_{nt, v}^i$ coefficients are often approximated with the net atomic populations; obviously, this implies to neglect the overlap population contributions to the photoionization cross-section. Now, even though σ_{2p}^C , σ_{2p}^O ,

and σ_{3d}^{Cr} ASPCS decrease upon the He(I) $\rightarrow$ He(II) switching,¹⁰⁴⁻¹⁰⁵ such a decrease is more pronounced for the $2p^{C/O}$ AOs than for the $3d^{Cr}$ ones. We then expect that the $h\nu^{He(I)} \rightarrow h\nu^{He(II)}$ changing will be associated to a detectable weakening of the ¹PE features generated by the ionization from L-based MOs.

Spin-unrestricted NR Slater Transition State¹⁰⁶ (⁵TS) calculations for the spin $\uparrow$ $18a_1$ and $30e$ SOMOs have been carried out to approximately take care of the electronic structure relaxation upon ionization. ⁵TS outcomes ultimately confirm the assignment of the ¹PE Y feature to the ionization from “metal d-orbitals” as proposed by Van Dam and Oskam^{28b,107} on the basis of their He(II) measurements. More specifically, the weak and broad Y peak at ~ 7.5 eV appears to be generated by the ionization from the $30e(\uparrow)$ e_g -like SOMOs (⁵TS_{30e(↑)} = 6.84 eV), strongly mixed with the e_g -like ones (see Fig. 2), while ⁵TS results pertaining to the $18a_1(\uparrow)$ SOMO (⁵TS_{18a1(↑)} = 7.47 eV) suggest that its ionization is hidden under the lower IE side of the following PE feature (the band A centred at 8.06 eV in the He(I) ¹PE spectrum recorded by Evans *et al.*^{28a}) together the ionization from the π_3 acac-based $15a_2$ DOMO whose IE appears to be substantially TM independent¹⁰⁹ (8.06,^{28a} 8.14,^{28a} 8.10,^{28a} and 8.18^{28d} eV in **I**, **II**, **III**, and Al(acac)₃, respectively) as a consequence of the absence of any 3d AO transforming as the a_2 IR in the D_3 symmetry point group.

The electronic structure of **II**, when compared to **I**, is characterized by the presence of an extra electron. According to our preliminary qualitative considerations, such an electron will i) asymmetrically occupy the Mn 3d-based e_g -like orbitals; ii) induce the already mentioned genuine Jahn-Teller distortion characterizing the γ structure of **II**;^{19c} iii) lift the degeneracy of the Mn^{III} 3d-based e_g -like levels. Similarly to **I**, ¹GS ADF results confirm our prediction indicating the $94a(\uparrow)$ ¹HOMO and the $95a(\uparrow)$ ¹LUMO (see the central panel of Fig. 2) as the Mn^{III} e_g -like orbitals (strongly mixed with the e_g -like ones), which account for the σ Mn–O antibonding interaction with the e linear combination of the acac-based n . FMO (see Figs. 3, 5 and 6). Incidentally, the bonding partners of the $94a(\uparrow)$ ¹HOMO and the $95a(\uparrow)$ ¹LUMO correspond to the $85a$ and $86a$ DOMOs whose spin $\uparrow$ components lie at -6.98 and -6.88 eV, respectively (see Figs. 2 and 3). Despite the absence of any symmetry element, it is then possible not only to recognize t_{2g} - and e_g -like orbitals among the frontier MOs of **II** but also to assess that the former set appears much more atom-like in **II** than in **I**, while the e_g -like contribution to the TM–L interaction is rather similar in the Cr^{III} and Mn^{III} complexes (see Figs. 2, 3 and 5).¹¹⁰

Fig. 6 3D plots of the 94a(↑) ¹¹HOMO and 95a(↑) ¹¹LUMO. Displayed isosurfaces correspond to $\pm 0.05 e^{3/2} \text{Å}^{-3/2}$ values.

Useful information about this matter may be gained by exploiting the ²TS⁶¹ scheme.¹¹¹ As a matter of fact, ¹¹BE is computed less negative than ¹BE by 27 kcal/mol (see Table 1), and two contributions oppositely participate to this finding: the ΔE_{ster} term, lower in II than in I as a consequence of the Jahn-Teller distortion,^{19c,58} and the ΔE_{int} term, much less negative in II than in I (the absence of any symmetry element in II prevents any further ΔE_{int} partitioning into contributions from distinct IRs). Besides the effects associated to the minor differences characterizing the structural arrangement of the (acac)₃³⁻ fragment around the TM^{III} ions (see Fig. 7), the $|\Delta E_{\text{int}}| < |\Delta E_{\text{int}}|$ result is directly related to the weakening of the TM–O interaction induced by the presence of the extra electron occupying the e_g-like 94a(↑) ¹¹HOMO,¹¹⁰ whose antibonding character with respect to the σ Mn–O interaction has been already stressed. Taking I as a reference once again, it is interesting to note that ¹¹I^{NM} $\sim$ ¹I^{NM} when considering the (Mn–O)⁵ bonds, while ¹¹I^{NM} $\sim$ 1/2 ¹I^{NM} for the (Mn–O)¹ ones (see Table 1). Such a result may be straightforwardly rationalized by looking at the 94a(↑) ¹¹HOMO and the 95a(↑) ¹¹LUMO 3D plots (see Fig. 6). Similarly to I, “only” the Mn 3d-based t_{2g}-like orbitals are involved in the four (Mn–O)⁵ bonds; while an e_g-like antibonding SOMO is also involved when the two (Mn–O)¹ ones are considered.

Fig. 7 Superimposed licorice representation of I (Cr^{III} ion in yellow), II (Mn^{III} ion in burgundy), and III (Fe atom in olive green) BP86 optimized structures. Hydrogen atoms of the acac fragments are not displayed for the sake of clarity.

Before moving to the analysis of the He(I) ¹¹PE features,^{28a,28f,98,99} it is worth of note that theoretical outcomes so far considered are perfectly in tune with structural data reported in Table 2, where selected optimized geometrical parameters for title complexes are compared with

corresponding X-ray crystallographic results^{8c,19b} and the DFT–B3LYP structures reported by Diaz-Acosta *et al.*^{8c–8d} (optimized coordinates of I, II and III are reported in Tables S1, S2 and S3 of the ESI,†, respectively). In more detail, the inspection of Table 2 reveals that BP86 structural parameters quantitatively agree with both the X-ray crystallographic results^{8c,19b} and DFT–B3LYP literature data.^{8c–8d} Incidentally, as already mentioned, the L geometrical parameters appear to be negligibly affected along the series (see Fig. 7).

Similarly to I, the spin-unrestricted NR ⁵TS calculations¹⁰⁶ carried out for the topmost spin $\uparrow$ MOs prompt us to assign with confidence the very weak He(I) γ feature of the ¹¹PE to the ionization from the 94a(↑) ¹¹HOMO ($\epsilon_{94a(\uparrow)}^{\text{TS}} = 6.34$ eV), i.e., the Mn 3d-based e_g-like SOMO antibonding in character with respect to the Mn–O σ interaction (see Fig. 6). As far as the broad band A and the evident shoulder on its lower IE side are concerned (see Fig. 1 of ref. 28f), they are together associated to the ionization from the three linear combinations of the π_3 acac-based FMOs (the 93a – 91a DOMOs). Two reasons concur to minimize the splitting between the e and the a₂ linear combinations of the π_3 acac-based FMOs revealed in I: i) the absence of any symmetry elements in II allows a similar participation of Mn 3d-based AOs ($\sim$ 11%) to the π_3 -based spin $\uparrow$ MOs; ii) the Mn t_{2g}-like SOMOs are more atom-like in II than in I (see Fig. 2), so that their interaction with π_3 -based spin $\uparrow$ MOs is poorer in II than in I (see Fig. 3).

Table 2 Selected optimized geometrical parameters for I – III. Bond lengths and bond angles are in Å and deg, respectively. Beside X-ray values (in parentheses),^{8c–10b} theoretical B3LYP literature values^{8c–8d} (in bold) are also reported for comparison.^a

	M–O	C–O	C–C	O–M–O ^b	M–O–C
I	1.977 / 1.977 (1.953)	1.273 / 1.272 (1.260)	1.405 / 1.403 (1.385)	91.5 / 89.7 (91.1)	126.4 / 128.0 (126.7)
II	1.928 / 1.941 / 2.163 1934 / 1.951 / 2.147 (1.932 / 1.937 / 2.110)	1.273 ^c 1.276^c (1.268) ^c	1.406 ^c 1.405^c (1.384) ^c	89.5 ^c 89.2^c (89.2) ^c	126.6 ^c 127.7^c (127.0) ^c
III	2.014 / 2.011 (1.992)	1.272 / 1.275 (1.262)	1.405 / 1.405 (1.382)	87.5 / 87.4 (87.4)	129.3 / 129.8 (129.1)

^aLiterature values pertaining to I and III are those reported in ref. 8c, while those pertaining to II are taken from refs. 19b (X-ray) and 8d (B3LYP). ^bIt refers to the angle within the pseudoaromatic ring. ^cMean value.

The symmetric occupation of the 31e ¹¹HOMO prevents any Jahn-Teller⁵⁸ distortions of the ¹¹GS structure and, despite the absence of any doubt about the 31e ¹¹HOMO nature (strongly antibonding in character with respect to the Fe–O σ interaction, see Figs. 3, 5 and 8), it deserves to be underlined that the overall participation of the Fe 3d AOs to the 31e ¹¹HOMO amounts to 33% with a comparable contribution of ^et_{2g} (19%) and e_g-like (14%) levels. It is then at least hasty to label the ¹¹HOMO as Fe 3d-based SOMOs.^{29a} Even more unlikely appears the assessment of a SOMO nature^{29a} for the 30e MO, whose localization on the Fe 3d-based AOs appears negligible (see Fig. 6 of the ref. 29a). As such, the antibonding nature of the Fe e_g-like spin $\uparrow$ MOs (see Figs. 3, 5 and 8) and the “non-bonding” character of the Fe t_{2g}-like ones (see Fig. 3), makes hard to justify not only the close spacing between ^et_{2g}

and e_g -like SOMOs but also the rather large ΔE (~ 2 eV) between ${}^e t_{2g}$ and ${}^a t_{2g}$ SOMOs (see Fig. 6 of the ref. 29a).

Fig. 8 3D plots of the $31e(\uparrow)$ HOMO. Displayed isosurfaces correspond to $\pm 0.05 e^{1/2} \text{Å}^{-3/2}$ values.

Similarly to I and II, the BP86 optimized structural parameters of III agree very well with both the X-ray crystallographic results and the DFT–B3LYP structures reported by Diaz-Acosta *et al.*^{8c} (see Table 2). Interestingly, the Fe–O bond distances are intermediate between the Cr–O and the (Mn–O)^I ones. Such a result, perfectly mirrored by the corresponding ${}^{\text{III}}I^{\text{NM}}$ value, is the consequence of the presence of two electrons in the two e_g -like($\uparrow$) SOMOs (the bonding partners correspond once again to the $28e(\uparrow)$ MOs, whose localization on the Fe^{III} e_g -like AOs amounts to 48%, see figs. 2 and 3). Incidentally, the larger I^{NM} decrease upon moving from I to II than from I to III is simply due to the different localization of the $94a(\uparrow)$ (in II) and $31e(\uparrow)$ (in III) SOMOs (compare the corresponding 3D plots in Figs. 6 and 8, respectively). According to that, ${}^{\text{III}}BE$ is evaluated less negative than ${}^{\text{I}}BE$ by 61 kcal/mol (see Table 1), and the major role in determining such an evidence is the reduced e contribution (~ 100 kcal/mol) to ΔE_{int} as a consequence of the antibonding character of the symmetrically occupied $31e(\uparrow)$ HOMO.

Before considering the lowest lying He(I) ${}^{\text{III}}PE$ spectrum assignment, two further remarks have to be done: i) as qualitatively anticipated by Pritchard and Autschbach,⁹⁰ only the spin $\downarrow$ component of the $(\text{acac})_3^{3-}$ -based n . FMOs concur to the dative $L \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$ bonding (see Fig. 5); ii) even though the Fe–O interaction is certainly the most covalent among the investigated molecules (see the $Q_{\text{iv}}^{\text{Fe}}$ and $Q_{\text{vor}}^{\text{Fe}}$ values in Table 1 and consider the 48% participation of the Fe^{III} e_g -like AOs to the $28e(\uparrow)$ MOs), the overall effect of such an increased symmetry-restricted covalency⁴⁷ is the Fe–O bond weakening.

Besides the already mentioned differences between the He(I) ${}^{\text{III}}PE$ spectra recorded by the British^{28a}/Canadian^{28e} research groups and that of Vovna^{28c,28f} in the IE region ranging from 9.22 to 10.16 eV, it has to be also underlined that the He(I) ${}^{\text{III}}PE$ spectrum recorded by the Russians (see Fig. 1 of the ref. 28f), similarly to II, seems to be characterized by the presence of an almost imperceptible feature at low IEs. In this context, it is of some relevance to remind the literature debate between the Lloyd and Orchard groups about the “weak low-ionisation-energy band in the He(I) photoelectron spectrum of $\text{Fe}(\text{hfa})_3$ ”, which took place early in the seventies.^{112,113} Spin unrestricted NR ${}^{\text{S}}TS$ calculations¹⁰⁶ carried out for the

symmetrically occupied $31e(\uparrow)$ HOMO provide a theoretical estimate of the lowest IE (${}^{\text{S}}TS_{31e(\uparrow)} = 6.95$ eV) which would prompt us to agree with the Lloyd’s assignment,⁹⁹ even though the presence of a shadow of the prominent PE band A¹¹³ cannot be ruled out.

3.2 Unoccupied Electronic Structure. Dipole allowed transitions imply that³⁷

$$\Gamma_{\text{GS}} \otimes \Gamma_{\mu} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{ES}} \supset \Gamma_{\text{Sym}} \quad (2)$$

where Γ_{GS} , Γ_{ν} , Γ_{ES} and Γ_{Sym} correspond to the IRs of the $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_3$ electronic GS (a_2 in I, e in II, and a_1 in III),⁵⁷ the dipole moment operator ($a_2 + e$),³⁷ the electronic ES ($\Gamma_{\text{iso}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{GS}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}}$),⁸⁴ and the totally symmetric representation (a_1) of the idealized $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_3$ point group (D_3), respectively. Eqn (2) may then evolve to

$$\Gamma_{\text{GS}} \otimes a_2 \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{GS}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} = a_2 \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} \supset a_1 \quad (3a)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{GS}} \otimes e \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{GS}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} = e \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} \supset a_1 \quad (3b)$$

pointing out that, within the approximation, which reduces the complete one-electron excited configuration space ($1h-1p$ space) to the subspace where only the core electrons are excited, the allowed electric dipole transitions imply

$$\Gamma_{\text{iso}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} = a_2 \quad (4a)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{iso}} \otimes \Gamma_{\text{iso}} = e \quad (4b)$$

In the D_3 point group, electric dipole transitions forbidden by symmetry are then limited to the $a_1 \rightarrow a_1$ and $a_2 \rightarrow a_2$ ones.³⁷

Wang and Ziegler¹¹³ have shown that spin-unrestricted TD-DFT calculations are able to provide a rather accurate evaluation of EEs even when dealing with open shell molecules.^{49b} Lowest lying electronic excitations from the $1s^0$ -based DOMOs (the $3a_1 + 2a_2 + 2e + 3e$ $\text{TM}(\text{acac})_3$ orbitals, $\text{TM} = \text{Cr}$ and Fe)¹¹⁴ will involve transitions to: i) TM based ${}^a t_{2g}$ and ${}^e t_{2g}$ SOMOs,⁷ ii) TM based e_g -like VMOs/SOMOs,⁷ iii) linear combinations of the acac -based π_{4} VMO. Along the whole I – III series, transitions from the $1s^0$ -based DOMOs to the ${}^a t_{2g}$ and ${}^e t_{2g}$ SOMOs⁷ cannot affect the GS spin multiplicities. In fact, ESS associated to the $t_{2g}^4 e_g^0$ (I), $t_{2g}^4 e_g^1$ (II), and $t_{2g}^4 e_g^2$ (III) excited electronic configurations will necessarily correspond to quartets in I, quintets in II and sextets in III, if spin contamination is neglected. The same holds for transitions from the $1s^0$ -based DOMOs to the e_g -like SOMOs⁷ in III. The situation is much more complicated when VMOs are involved; i.e., Cr^{III}/Mn^{III} 3d-based e_g -like orbitals or linear combinations of the acac -based $\pi_{e/o}$ FMOs. For instance, in I the $3a_1^2 \dots 32e^0 \rightarrow 3a_1^1 \dots 32e^1$ electronic excitation (the $32e$ MO corresponds to the Cr^{III} e_g -like VMOs) may generate one sextet state (6E), two quartet states (4E), and a doublet state (2E). Quartet $\rightarrow$ sextet and quartet $\rightarrow$ doublet excitations, implying spin-flip or double excitation processes, will be ignored herein and, similarly to our studies on the CuPc ,^{64e} CuTPP ^{64g} and

CuTPP(F)^{64g} ^NK-edges, the ^OK-edge spectra of title compounds will be assigned by limiting our attention to excitations involving the same GS spin multiplicity.⁷

Upon 2p → 3d one-electron excitation, the TM^{III} final electronic configuration is 2p⁵3d⁴ in I, 2p⁵3d⁵ in II and 2p⁵3d⁶ in III. If the whole set of multiplets arising from the 3d^{4/6} (3d⁵) configurations is collectively labelled as D^{4/6} (D⁵),¹¹⁶ the electronic states generated by the 2p⁵3d^{4/6} (2p⁵3d⁵) configuration are: ²P ⊗ D⁴ = ^{2,4}S, ^{2,4,6}P, ^{2,4,6}D, ^{2,4,6}F, ^{2,4}G, ^{2,4}H, ^{2,4}I, ²K (2P ⊗ D⁵ = ^{1,3,5}S, ^{1,3,5,7}P, ^{1,3,5}D, ^{1,3,5}F, ^{1,3,5}G, ^{1,3,5}H, ^{1,3}I, ^{1,3}K).¹¹⁶ As a consequence of the ligand-field, covalent interactions and SOC admixture, these states will further split to generate a total of 6 × 210 = 1260 (6 × 252 = 1512) molecular magnetic spin sublevels with M_S = ±1/2, ±3/2, ±5/2 (M_S = 0, ±1, ±2, ±3). Reference to the TM^{III} electronic configuration in I, II, and III⁷ allows us to foresee that the one-electron excitation pattern describing Cr^{III} and Mn^{III} final states in the D₃ structure will include states having spin multiplicity either equal to (ΔS = 0) or lower/higher than (ΔS = ±1) the GS one (¹S = 3/2; ³S = 2), a consequence of the presence of empty 3d-based MOs in both cases.¹²⁰ At variance to that, the one-electron excitation pattern describing the Fe^{III} final states will be dominated by states having a spin multiplicity equal to (ΔS = 0) or lower than (ΔS = -1) the GS one (⁴S = 5/2).¹²⁰ We showed elsewhere⁴⁸ that these excitations involve mainly DOMO → SOMO transitions.

3.2.1 O K-edge spectra. The pre-edge EE region of the ^OK-edge spectra of title molecules is displayed in Figs. 9 for the D₃ I and III and in Fig. 10 for the C₁ II.

Fig. 9 Experimental (upper panels) and simulated (lower panels) ^OK-edge spectra of I (left panels) and III (right panels). Contributions from a₂ and e symmetries in the SR ZORA TD-DFT 1s^o excitation spectra of I and III are also displayed. 1s^o SR-ZORA ionization limits evaluated by adopting the LB94 functional⁶⁹ are 534.9 eV (I) and 534.6 eV(III). Both simulated spectra have been shifted by 12.2 eV and have a Gaussian broadening of 0.4 eV.

It has been already mentioned³⁸ that the electric dipole allowed³⁷ 1s^l → mp^l transitions intensity quantifies the participation of the L donor atom mp AOs to the unoccupied frontier MOs.^{28,44-46} Unfortunately, it was not possible to obtain a reliable quantitative comparison of the experimental intensities because of the significantly different thickness of

the molecular films, which likely yielded different morphologies.

Fig. 10 Experimental and simulated ^OK-edge spectra of II. The 1s^o SR-ZORA ionization limit evaluated by adopting the LB94 functional⁶⁹ is 534.8 eV (mean value). Theoretical EEs have been shifted by 12.6 eV and reported as vertical steaks because the optimized structure of II has no symmetry.

Along the whole I – III series, the ^OK pre-edge EE region appears as an asymmetric broad and intense band centred at ~ 531.5 eV followed by a much less intense feature at ~ 535 eV. The main peak (A, in Figs 9 and 10) has a rather similar shape in I and II, while the details of the spectral pattern of III appear quite different with respect to those of I and II (compare the upper panels of Fig. 9 and the spectrum reported in Fig. 10). In fact, both in I and II a shoulder S (much more evident in I) is present on the higher EE side of A, while an equally evident shoulder is present only on the lower EE side of A in III. All together, it is patent that the experimental information provided by ^OK-edge spectra is not particularly reach. Thus, only the combined use of symmetry, orbitals and spectra appears to be the Hobson's choice to get some information from the experimental evidences.

EEs and *f* values associated with the 1s^o excitation spectrum as obtained from spin-unrestricted SR-ZORA TD-DFT calculations carried for I, II and III are reported in Tables S4 – S6, respectively, of the ESI,[†] while the corresponding ^V_{III}*f* distributions in the EE range 528 – 537 eV are displayed in Fig. 9 (lower panels), where e + a₂ contributions are also included, and Fig. 10. The agreement between the 1s^o excitation spectrum of I and the ^V_{III}*f* distribution is amazing. Theoretical results included in Table S4 of the ESI,[†] allow us to assign with confidence the main feature A of the ^OK-edge NEXAFS spectrum of I to states generated by the two lowest lying and accidentally degenerate 1s^o → π₄ transitions, both of them characterized by a not negligible (> 20%) ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) contribution involving the ^a_{2g} 18a₁(↓) ^lLUMO. As far as the shoulder S on the higher EE side of A is concerned, major contributions come from states associated to 1s^o → e_g-like LMCT excitations. According to spin-unrestricted SR-ZORA TD-DFT results, high lying VMOs are involved in states contributing to B.

Even though the absence of any symmetry elements in the optimized structure of II does not allow a straightforward

distinction between e and a_2 excitations, the overall agreement between theory and experiment is once again startling (see Fig. 10). Interestingly, the lower EE side of the main feature A is generated by states all of them involving $1s^0 \rightarrow 95a(\uparrow)$ LUMO (see Fig. 6) LMCT excitations. Moreover, similarly to I, two quasi degenerate excitations contribute to A in the $1s^0$ XA spectrum of II. Even though major contributions come in both cases from $1s^0 \rightarrow \pi_4$ transitions, the LMCT contribution cannot be neglected. As such, the excitation with $f = 18.6 \times 10^{-3}$, besides π_4 , also involve t_{2g} -like($\downarrow$) levels as fsos, while the fso involved in the excitation with $f = 14.7 \times 10^{-3}$ correspond the empty e_g -like $95a(\uparrow)$ LUMO (see Table S5 of the ESI,[†]). At least four transitions are present on the higher EE side of A (see Table S5 of the ESI,[†]); besides the prevalent involvement of $1s^0 \rightarrow \pi_4$ excitations, all of them also imply LMCT $1s^0 \rightarrow t_{2g}$ -like($\downarrow$) contributions.

It has been already mentioned that the 0K -edge NEXAFS spectrum of III reveals minor, but well evident, differences with respect to the spectral patterns of I and II. The agreement between theory and experiment (see Fig. 9, left panels) makes us confident about the possibility of shedding light into this matter. EE s and f values associated with the $1s^0$ excitation spectrum as obtained from spin-unrestricted SR-ZORA TD-DFT calculations carried for III are reported in Tables S6 of the ESI,[†] while the $^m f$ distribution in the EE range 528 – 537 eV is displayed in Fig. 9, where $e + a_2$ contributions are also included. Data included in Table S6 of the ESI,[†] allow us to assign with confidence the shoulder S on the lower EE side of the main feature A to states generated by two distinct $1s^0 \rightarrow t_{2g}$ -like($\downarrow$) LMCT transitions. Several, closely spaced excitations contribute to A (see Table S6 of the ESI,[†]); among them, the ones characterized by the largest $^m f$ values (33.4×10^{-3} and 34.9×10^{-3}) are accidentally degenerate and characterized by the $1s^0 \rightarrow \pi_4$ contributions comparable to the $1s^0 \rightarrow e_g$ -like($\downarrow$) ones.

3.2.1 TM^{III} $L_{2,3}$ -edges spectra. The simulated $L_{2,3}$ -edges spectrum is compared in Fig. 11 with the experimental one.

Fig. 11 Simulated (black solid line) and experimental (black dotted line) $L_{2,3}$ -edges spectrum of I. Blue, green and red lines represent deconvolution of the simulated

spectrum in terms of states with different spin multiplicity (S). The simulated spectrum has been shifted by 3.2 eV and has a Gaussian broadening of 1.0 eV.

Despite relative positions and shapes of the L_3 features are correctly reproduced, the opposite is true when the L_3^1 and L_3^2 relative intensities are considered. As such, it is noteworthy that in the “L-edge X-ray absorption study of mononuclear vanadium complexes and spectral predictions using a restricted open shell configuration interaction ansatz” Maganas *et al.*^{42j} pointed out that the relative intensity of the simulated lowest lying L_3 feature of the $V(acac)_3$ XA spectrum is dramatically influenced by the adopted functional and the selected semi-empirical parameters c_1 , c_2 , and c_3 (see the panel C of Fig. 5 in ref. 42j). Here, rather than adopting different functionals or different c_1 , c_2 , and c_3 values for different species to obtain the best agreement between theory and experiment, we preferred to adopt, throughout the paper, the same functional and the same set of c_1 , c_2 , and c_3 values to favour the comparison between homogeneous theoretical results.

The inspection of Fig. 11 testifies that most relevant contributions to the lower L_3 EE region (below 571 eV) arise from states having either GS ($S = 3/2$, $\Delta S = 0$) or lower ($S = 1/2$, $\Delta S = -1$) spin multiplicity. Moreover, states associated to the L_3^1 ($S = 3/2$, >95%) and L_3^2 ($S = 3/2$, 62%) features lying at $EE = 568.6$ and 570.2 eV, respectively, mainly involve Cr^{III} -based $2p \rightarrow ^{a/e}t_{2g}$ single electronic excitations. The successive broad and intense band envelope centred at 572.5 eV consists of two evident features, L_3^3 and L_3^4 at $EE = 571.9$ and 572.5 eV, respectively. States with $\Delta S = 0$ and $\Delta S = \pm 1$ (28, 34 and 15%, respectively, see Fig. 11) similarly contribute to L_3^3 , while L_3^4 mainly include (57%) states with $\Delta S = 0$. In more detail, states having the GS spin multiplicity and contributing to L_3^3 involve Cr^{III} -based single (16%) $2p \rightarrow ^e t_{2g}$ transitions and coupled-single^{42j} (84%) $2p \rightarrow ^{a/e}t_{2g}$ SOMOs and $^{a/e}t_{2g}$ SOMOs $\rightarrow e_g$ -like VMOs excitations. At variance to that, states with $S = 5/2$ ($\Delta S = +1$) and $S = 1/2$ ($\Delta S = -1$) mainly involve single $2p \rightarrow \pi_4$ metal-to-ligand charge transfer (MLCT) transitions. States with $\Delta S = 0$ (57%) and contributing to L_3^4 involve the same, just mentioned, $2p \rightarrow ^{a/e}t_{2g}$ SOMOs and $^{a/e}t_{2g} \rightarrow e_g$ -like coupled-single excitations. As far as the highest EE peak of the L_3 region (L_3^5 at $EE = 574.6$ eV in Fig. 11) is concerned, it mainly includes (66%) states with $\Delta S = 0$, which involve coupled-single electronic excitations. Nevertheless, it has to be underlined that these transitions now correspond to $2p \rightarrow ^{a/e}t_{2g}$ and $^{a/e}t_{2g}$ SOMOs $\rightarrow \pi_4$ VMOs MLCT excitations and differently from $Mn(acac)_2$,⁴⁸ $Co(acac)_2$,⁴⁸ $FePc$ ¹²² and $FePc(\eta^2-O_2)$ ¹²² do not imply states with $\Delta S = -1$.

It is well known that main discrepancies between theory and experiment affect the L_2 region;^{42j} nevertheless, it is of some relevance to mention that the DFT/ROCIS $L_2^2 - L_3^3$ ΔEE (7 eV) satisfactorily reproduces the experimental value (7.5 eV). Any further assignment of the L_2 feature is herein avoided as this EE region is not unambiguously determined by experiment.^{42j}

The $^{II}L_{2,3}$ -edges NEXAFS spectrum, first recorded by Grush *et al.*,¹²³ is superimposed to the simulated one in Figure 12.

The overall agreement between theory and experiment is definitely better than that obtained for I. In fact, not only the relative energy positions and the shape of the simulated L_3 features nicely match the experimental evidences, but also their relative intensities are properly reproduced by DFT/ROCIS calculations. As a whole, the ${}^{II}L_3$ spectrum is characterized by the presence of four spectral features. Similarly to I, the lowest lying ones (${}^{II}L_3^1$ and ${}^{II}L_3^2$ at $EE = 639.5$ and 640.8 eV, respectively) are dominated (90 and 69%, respectively) by states having the same GS multiplicity and involving Mn^{III} -based $2p \rightarrow 3d$ electronic excitations. In more detail, the ${}^{II}L_3^1$ shoulder involves only $2p \rightarrow a^1e_t_{2g}$ SOMOs transitions, while the most intense ${}^{II}L_3^2$ peak also involves the $2p \rightarrow e_g$ -like SOMO excitation. Incidentally, states with $\Delta S = -1$ and involving $2p \rightarrow VMO$ MLCT transition faintly (14%) contribute to ${}^{II}L_3^2$. Alike ${}^{II}L_3^1$ and ${}^{II}L_3^2$, states with $\Delta S = 0$ mainly contribute (51%) to the generation of the ${}^{II}L_3^3$ feature at 642.7 eV; nevertheless, coupled-single $2p \rightarrow$ SOMOs and SOMOs $\rightarrow$ VMO electronic excitations are predominant (86%). It is worthwhile to mention that, both the SOMOs ($a^1e_t_{2g}$ and e_g -like) and the VMO (e_g -like), are Mn^{III} 3d-based MOs. As far as the remaining 14% is concerned, it is generated by the $2p \rightarrow e_g$ -like SOMO excitation. Even though tiny, contributions to ${}^{II}L_3^3$ from states with $\Delta S = +1/-1$ (15%/11%) cannot be ignored and they mainly involve $2p \rightarrow$ VMOs MLCT transitions (see Fig. 12). States having the GS spin multiplicity ($\Delta S = 0$) highly contribute (69%) to the highest lying ${}^{II}L_3^4$ feature at 645.2 eV, and likewise ${}^{II}L_3^3$ both coupled-single (81%) and single (19%) electronic excitations are involved. Nevertheless, similarly to I, VMOs systematically correspond to the linear combinations of the π_4 acac-based FMO.

Fig. 12 Experimental (black dotted line) and simulated (black solid line) $L_{2,3}$ -edges spectra of II. Blue, green and red lines represent deconvolution of the simulated spectrum in terms of states with different spin multiplicity (S). The simulated spectrum has been shifted by 10.0 eV and has a Gaussian broadening 1.8 eV. Experimental spectrum was digitalized from the ref. 122.

In more detail, both the single electronic excitations ($2p \rightarrow \pi_4$) and the coupled-single $2p \rightarrow a^1e_t_{2g}$ and e_g -like $\rightarrow \pi_4$ transitions have a MLCT character. As a final remark, states with $\Delta S = \pm 1$ contribute to the ${}^{II}L_3^2$ and ${}^{II}L_3^3$ central peaks (see

Fig. 12), represent a 27% of the total transitions and mainly involve high-lying acac-based VMOs. The theoretical ΔEE between ${}^{II}L_2^1$ and ${}^{II}L_3^2$ (10 eV) semiquantitatively reproduce the experimental value (~ 11 eV),¹²²⁻¹²³ but no further assignment of ${}^{II}L_2$ features is herein attempted as this region is not unambiguously determined by experiment.

The ${}^{III}L_{2,3}$ -edges NEXAFS spectrum^{8h} is superimposed to the simulated one in Fig. 13. The overall agreement is very good; positions, shapes and relative intensities of experimental features are properly reproduced both in the in ${}^{III}L_3$ and ${}^{III}L_2$ regions. The well defined, lowest lying L_3^1 peak ($EE = 708.3$ eV) mainly includes (94%) states characterized by $\Delta S = 0$ and generated by $2p \rightarrow a^1e_t_{2g}$ SOMOs single electronic excitations. Even though both states with $\Delta S = 0$ and $\Delta S = -1$ contribute to the most intense peak L_3^2 ($EE = 710.1$ eV), the former (75%) significantly exceed the latter (see Fig. 13) and they are associated to $2p \rightarrow e_g$ -like single electronic excitations. As far as states with $\Delta S = -1$ are concerned, the involve MLCT transitions from the whole Fe^{III} $2p$ set to the e linear combination of the acac-based π_4 FMO.

On the higher energy side of L_3^2 there are two well evident shoulders (${}^{III}L_3^3$ and ${}^{III}L_3^4$ at 711.8 and 713.5 eV, respectively). Both states with $\Delta S = 0$ and $\Delta S = -1$ contribute to the ${}^{III}L_3^3$ (51% vs 27%, respectively); moreover, Fe^{III} -based single electronic excitations ($2p \rightarrow e_g$ -like) are involved in $\Delta S = 0$ states, while MLCT $2p \rightarrow \pi_4$ transitions contribute to $\Delta S = -1$ states. Very similar considerations can be done for electronic excitations associated to states generating ${}^{III}L_3^4$, the only difference being the higher percentage of states with $\Delta S = -1$ (59%) with respect to those characterize by the GS spin multiplicity (34%).

Fig. 13 Experimental (black dotted line) and simulated (black solid line) $L_{2,3}$ -edges spectra of III. Blue and red lines represent deconvolution of the simulated spectrum in terms of states with different spin multiplicity (S). The simulated spectrum has been shifted by 10.3 eV and has a Gaussian broadening 1.2 eV. Experimental spectrum was digitalized from the ref. 8h.

As already mentioned, DFT/ROCIS calculations quantitatively reproduce the ${}^{III}L_2 - {}^{III}L_3$ ΔEE (~ 13 eV, see Fig. 13), but for the same reasons previously underlined we do not attempt any detailed assignment of this EE region.

Conclusions

Occupied and empty states of HS Cr(acac)₃, Mn(acac)₃, and Fe(acac)₃ complexes have been thoroughly investigated. Ground states of the three complexes have been comparatively studied by considering the same octahedral coordinative environment of the TM^{III} ion, the same oxidation number of the TM^{III} ion, the same number of TMt_{2g}-like electrons, and the progressive increasing of the TMe_g-like electron number. The TM–L bonding scheme of the D₃ Cr(acac)₃ appears to be dominated by ionic interactions, while the D₃ Fe(acac)₃ results the most covalent among the investigated complexes. Despite such an evidence, the use of the Ziegler transition state approach allowed us to state that the Fe(acac)₃ bonding energy is significantly lower than the Cr(acac)₃ one as a consequence of the symmetric occupation of the Fe 3d-based e_g-like orbitals, Fe–O σ antibonding in nature. Occupied frontier orbitals have been also studied by exploiting vapour-phase He(I) and, when available, He(II) literature PE data. Experimental evidences, nowadays not yet definitely assigned, have been discussed and compared with the outcomes of numerical experiments carried out in the framework of the DFT and by exploiting the Slater transition state method. Insights into the title molecules empty states have been gained by combining NEXAFS data at the ^OK-edge as well as at the TML_{3,2}-edges with scalar relativistic ZORA TDDFT and DFT/ROCIS calculations, respectively. Similarly to other TM complexes characterized by the presence of ligands with low lying empty π* orbitals, the higher EE side of the ^{IVIII}L₃-edge systematically includes states, which involve metal-to-ligand-charge-transfer transitions. The good agreement between experiment and theory certainly encourages us to apply both approaches to different ligands and corresponding TM complexes when interested to look into K-edge and L_{3,2}-edges evidences.

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Notes and references

- 1 H. B. Gray, J. G. Swanson and T. H. Crawford, *Project Acac: An Experimental Investigation in Synthesis and Structure*, Bodgen and Quigley: New York 1972.
- 2 (a) R. C. Mehrotra, R. Bohra and D. P. Gaur, *Metal β-Diketonates and Allied Derivatives*, Academic Press, London, 1978; (b) R. C. Mehrotra, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1988, **35**, 1349.
- 3 D. P. Craig, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3175.
- 4 (a) F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry* 5th ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1988; (b) N. N. Greenwood and A. Earnshaw, *Chemistry of the Elements*, Butterworth-Heinemann, Cambridge, 2nd edn, 1984.

- 5 Symmetry properties of M(acac)₃ complexes with O atoms occupying the six vertices of a regular octahedron are described by the D₃ symmetry point group.
- 6 E. C. Lingafelter, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 151.
- 7 The electronic configurations of Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} in HS I, II and III, respectively, are: t_{2g}³e_g⁰ with S = 3/2 in I, t_{2g}³e_g¹ with S = 2 in II, t_{2g}³e_g² with S = 5/2 in III (S corresponds to the total spin angular momentum quantum number).
- 8 (a) G. C. Levy and R. A. Komoroski, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 678; (b) V. I. Vovna and A. I. Streltsov, *J. Struct. Chem.*, 1998, **39**, 917; (c) I. Diaz-Acosta, J. Baker, W. Cordes and P. Pulay, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2001, **105**, 238; (d) I. Diaz-Acosta, J. Baker, J. F. Hinton and P. Pulay, *Spectrochim. Acta A*, 2003, **59**, 363; (e) B. Pritchard and J. Autschbach, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 8340; (f) S. DeBeer George, T. Petrenko and F. Neese, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2008, **112**, 12936; (g) R. R. Sharp, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 2507; (h) E. C. Wasinger, F. M. de Groot, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and E. I. Solomon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2003, **125**, 12894; (i) *The Chemistry of Metal Enolates*, Ed. J. Zabicky, John Wiley and Sons, 2009; (j) S. S. Patil, S. V. Patil and V. D. Bobade, *Synlett.*, 2011, 2379.
- 9 (a) W. S. Rees, *CVD of Nonmetals*, VCH: New York, 1996, (b) T. Kodas and M. Hampden-Smith, *The Chemistry of Metal CVD*, VCH: New York, 1996; (c) *Thin Film Techniques and Applications*, Editors O. N. Sundaram, V. Veeravazhuthi, P. Meena, K. Tamil Selvan, 2004, New Delhi; (d) *Sol-Gel Methods for Materials Processing*, Editors P. Innocenzi, Y. L. Zub and V. G. Kessler, 2008, Springer Science; (e) R. A. Siddiqui, *Experimental Investigations of Thermodynamic Properties of Organometallic Compounds*, TUDpress, 2010; (f) Y. Xu and X.-T. Yan, *Chemical Vapour Deposition*, An Integrated Engineering Design for Advanced Materials, Springer, London, 2010; (g) B. D. Flockhart and D. Thorburn Burns, *Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1987, **59**, 915; (h) A. N. Kitaigorodskii, A. G. Stepanov and V. M. Nekipelov, *Magn. Res. Chem.*, 1986, **24**, 705.
- 10 I and III have been evocatively marked by Levy and Komoroski^{8a} more than forty years ago as “another powerful weapon in the chemists' arsenal for attacking organic structure problems”, being possible alternatives or complements to lanthanide shift reagents in NMR spectroscopy.
- 11 A. L. Willis, Z. Chen, J. He, Y. Zhu, N. J. Turro and S. O'Brien, *J. Nanomat.*, 2007, 14858.
- 12 K. Chokprasombat, C. Sirisathitkul, P. Harding, S. Chandarak, and R. Yimnirun, *J. Nanomat.*, 2012, 758429.
- 13 F. Pan and Q. Wang, *Molecules*, 2015, **20**, 20499.
- 14 A. Ejigu, P. A. Greatorex-Davies and D. A. Walsh, *Electrochem. Comm.*, 2015, **54**, 55.
- 15 J. D. Saraidaridis, B. M. Bartlett and C. W. Monroe, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2016, **163**, A1239.
- 16 Q. Liu, A. A. Shinkle, Y. Li, C. W. Monroe, L. T. Thompson and A. E. S. Sleigholme, *Electrochem. Comm.*, 2010, **12**, 1634.
- 17 (a) E. M. S. Maçoas, R. Kananavicius, P. Myllyperkiö, M. Pettersson and H. Kunttu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 8934, and references therein reported; (b) E. M. S. Maçoas, R. Kananavicius, P. Myllyperkiö, M. Pettersson and H. Kunttu, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2007, **111**, 2054; (c) E. M. S. Maçoas, S. Mustalahti, P. Myllyperkiö, H. Kunttu and M. Pettersson, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2015, **119**, 2727; (d) E. A. Juban and J. K. McCusker, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 6857; (e) E. A.

- Juban, A. L. Smeigh, J. E. Monat and J. McCusker, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 1783.
- 18 (a) F. Neese, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 10213; (b) A. R. Jaszewski, R. Stranger and R. Pace, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 2008, **112**, 11223; (c) L. Andjelkovic, M. Gruden-Pavlovic, C. Daul and M. Zlatar, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 2013, **113**, 859.
- 19 (a) J. P. Fackler and A. Avdeef, *Inorg. Chem.* 1974, **13**, 1864; (b) B. R. Stults, R. S. Marianelli and V. W. Day, *Inorg. Chem.* 1979, **18**, 1853; (c) J. Krzystek, G. J. Yeagle, J. H. Park, R. D. Britt, M. W. Meisel, L. C. Brunel and J. Telsler, *Inorg. Chem.* 2003, **42**, 4610.
- 20 R. van Gorkum, E. Bouwman and J. Reedijk, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 2456.
- 21 J. A. Takacs, G. V. Madhavan, M. Creswell, F. Seely and W. Devroy, *Organometal*, 1986, **5**, 2395.
- 22 R. A. Ligabue, A. L. Monteiro, R. F. de Souza and M. O. de Souza, *J. Mol. Cat. A: Chem.*, 1998, **130**, 101.
- 23 A. Sudo, S. Hirayama and T. Endo, *J. Poly. Sci. Poly. Chem.*, 2010, **48**, 479.
- 24 A. Misono, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1966, **39**, 2425.
- 25 K. T. Williamson and T. Yoon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 4570.
- 26 (a) J. Pinkas, V. Reichlova, R. Zboril, Z. Moravec, P. Bezdicka and J. Matejkova, *Ultrason. Sonochem.*, 2008, **15**, 257; (b) T. Hyeon, S. Seong Lee, J. Park, Y. Chung and H. B. Na, *J. Am. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 12798.
- 27 I. Rangeeka Perera, T. Daeneke, S. Makuta, Z. Yu, Y. Tachibana, A. Mishra, P. Bäuerle, C. A. Ohlin, U. Bach and L. Spiccia, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2015, **54**, 3758.
- 28 (a) S. Evans, A. Hamnett, A. F. Orchard and D. R. Lloyd, *Faraday Discuss. Chem. Soc.* 1972, **54**, 227; (b) H. Van Dam and A. Oskam, *J. Electron. Spectrosc.*, 1979, **17**, 353; (c) M. E. Akopyan, V. I. Vovna, V. I. Kleimenov, S. N. Lopatin and A. Yu. Ustinov, *Opt. Spectrosc. (USSR)*, 1990, **69**, 53; (d) A. Yu. Ustinov, V. I. Vovna, O. M. Ustinova, *J. Electron. Spectrosc.*, 1998, **88-91**, 103; (e) J. B. Westmore, M. L. J. Reimer, C. Reichert, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1991, **59**, 1797; (f) V. I. Vovna, I. B. Lvov, Y. V. Ivanov, S. N. Slabzhennikov, A. I. Streltsov and A. Yu. Ustinov, *J. Electron. Spectrosc.*, 1998, **96**, 141.
- 29 (a) M. M. Conradie, P. H. van Rooyen and J. Conradie, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 2013, **1053**, 134; (b) R. Liu and J. Conradie, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2015, **185**, 288.
- 30 G. L. Miessler, P. J. Fischer and D. A. Tarr, *Inorganic Chemistry*, Pearson, New York, 5th edn, 2013, p. 137.
- 31 According to their occupation numbers, MOs are divided in doubly occupied MOs (DOMOs), singly occupied MOs (SOMOs) and virtual (empty) MOs (VMOs). Moreover, HOMO and LUMO acronyms stand for highest occupied and lowest unoccupied MO, respectively.
- 32 (a) A. Bianconi, in *X-ray Absorption: Principles, Applications, Techniques of EXAFS, SEXAFS and XANES*, ed. D. C. Koningsberger and R. Prins, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1988, pp. 573-662; (b) J. Stöhr, *NEXAFS Spectroscopy*, Springer, Berlin, 1992.
- 33 H. H. Zhang, B. Hedman and K. O. Hodgson, in *Inorganic Electronic Structure*, ed. E. I. Solomon and A. B. P. Lever, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1999.
- 34 E. I. Solomon and C. B. Bell III, in *Physical Inorganic Chemistry, Principle, Methods and Models*, John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, 2010, pp. 1-37.
- 35 TMK-edge spectral features³⁶ are generated by the electric dipole forbidden, but quadrupole allowed $1s^M \rightarrow nd^M$ transitions,³⁷ which may be enhanced in non-centrosymmetric complexes through the involvement of $(n+1)p^M$ atomic orbitals (AOs) into frontier unoccupied MOs.³⁸ Differently to that, ^ML_{2,3}-edges structures³⁶ are dominated by electric dipole allowed $2p^{TM} \rightarrow nd^{TM}$ transitions,^{37,40} which question the contribution of nd^{TM} AOs to the unoccupied electronic structure. At variance to $1s^M \rightarrow nd^{TM}$ transitions, the $2p^6 \rightarrow nd^k$ ones produce a final electronic configuration with a hole in the $2p^{TM}$ core levels ($2p^5 nd^{k+1}$) whose orbital angular momentum quantum number $\ell = 1$. Spin-orbit coupling (SOC) allows the orbital angular momentum to couple with the spin angular momentum whose quantum number $s = 1/2$. SOC then generates two distinct states having total angular momentum quantum numbers $j = 3/2$ and $j = 1/2$. The former state lies at a lower excitation energy (EE) and it corresponds to the L₃ feature,³⁶ whose intensity is approximately twice the one of the L₂ feature³⁶ associated to the $j = 1/2$ state. Both the experimental analysis and the theoretical modelling of TML_{2,3}-edges spectra in TM complexes are challenging issues. In fact, besides ligand-field and covalency effects, the SOC between the numerous possible final-state multiplets has to be taken into account.^{41,42} TMK-edge and TML_{2,3}-edges outcomes of TM complexes may be eventually complemented by L donor atom K-edge (^OK-edge in the present case) evidences.⁴³ As a matter of fact, ^LK-edge spectra of TM complexes with partly filled nd atomic orbitals (AOs) are usually typified by rather intense pre-edge features generated by the electric dipole allowed³⁷ $1s^L \rightarrow mp^L$ transitions whose intensity quantifies the participation of the L donor atom mp AOs to the unoccupied frontier MOs.^{28,44-46} NEXAFS at the ^LK-edge then provides a direct probe of the so-called TM-L symmetry restricted covalency.⁴⁷
- 36 The absorption edges are labelled in the order of increasing energy, K, L₁, L₂, L₃, M₁,..., corresponding to the excitation of an electron from the $1s$ ($S_{1/2}$), $2s$ ($S_{1/2}$), $2p$ ($P_{1/2}$), $2p$ ($P_{3/2}$), $3s$ ($S_{1/2}$), ... orbitals (states), respectively.
- 37 B. E. Douglas and C. A. Hollingsworth, *Symmetry in Bonding and Spectra, an Introduction*; Academic Press, Inc.: Orlando, 1985; pp 256-257.
- 38 The ^MK-pre-edge is sensitive to 4p-3d mixing on the order of 1%, thus providing a rather accurate estimate of such a mixing.³⁹
- 39 S. DeBeer George, P. Brant, E. I. Solomon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 667.
- 40 The L₁-edge of the first transition series M is weak and provides poor spectroscopic information.⁴¹
- 41 R. K. Hocking and E. I. Solomon, *Struct. Bonding*, 2012, **142**, 155.
- 42 (a) F. de Groot, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2005, **249**, 31; (b) F. de Groot and A. Kotani, *Core Level Spectroscopy of Solids*, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2008; (c) M. Roemelt and F. Neese, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2013, **117**, 3069; (d) P. S. Bagus, H. Freund, H. Kühlenbeck and E. S. Ilton, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2008, **455**, 331; (e) H. Ikeno, T. Mizoguchi and I. Tanaka, *Phys. Rev. B: Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.*, 2011, **83**, 155107; (f) I. Josefsson, K. Kunnus, S. Schreck, A. Föhlisch, F. de Groot, P. Wernet and M. Odelius, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, 2012, **3**, 3565; (g) D. Maganas, M. Roemelt, M. Hävecker, A. Trunschke, A. Knop-Gericke, R. Schlögl and F. Neese, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, **15**, 7260; (h) M. Roemelt, D. Maganas, S. DeBeer and F. Neese, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, **138**, 204101; (i) D. Maganas, S. DeBeer and F. Neese, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2014, **53**, 6374; (j) D. Maganas, M. Roemelt, T. Weyhermüller, R.

- Blume, M. Hävecker, A. Knop-Gericke, S. DeBeer, R. Schlögl and F. Neese, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2014, **16**, 264.
- 43 (a) B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and E. I. Solomon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 1643; (b) S. E. Shadle, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and E. I. Solomon, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 4235; (c) S. E. Shadle, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and E. I. Solomon, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 7; (d) F. Neese, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and E. I. Solomon, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1999, **38**, 4854.
- 44 The higher the intensity, the higher the contribution of the L donor atoms to the unoccupied frontier MOs and, accordingly, the M–L covalent character.
- 45 T. Glaser, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson and E. I. Solomon, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2000, **33**, 859.
- 46 E. I. Solomon, B. Hedman, K. O. Hodgson, A. Deya and R. K. Szilagyic, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2005, **249**, 97.
- 47 C. K. Jørgensen (*Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding in Complexes*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, UK, 1962, p. 77) defined the symmetry-restricted covalency as the effect associated to the dilution, ruled by the complex symmetry, of d orbitals to make them become linear combinations of AOs (LCAO-MOs).
- 48 S. Carlotto, M. Sambì, A. Vittadini and M. Casarin *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2016, **18**, 2242.
- 49 (a) G. Mangione, L. Pandolfo, M. Sambì, G. Ligorio, M. V. Nardi, A. Cossaro, L. Floreano and M. Casarin, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2015, 2707 and references therein reported; (b) M. Rancan, J. Tessarolo, M. Casarin, P. L. Zanonato, S. Quici and L. Armelao, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2014, **53**, 7276.
- 50 F. Neese, *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev.: Comput. Mol. Sci.*, 2012, **2**, 73.
- 51 F. Wang, T. Ziegler, E. van Lenthe, S. van Gisbergen and E. J. Baerends, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2005, **122**, 204103.
- 52 S. Hirata and M. Head-Gordon, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1999, **314**, 291.
- 53 (a) E. van Lenthe, E. J. Baerends and J. G. Snijders, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **99**, 4597; (b) E. van Lenthe, E. J. Baerends and J. G. Snijders, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1994, **101**, 9783; (c) E. van Lenthe, A. Ehlers and E. J. Baerends, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1999, **110**, 8943.
- 54 H. Ando, S. Iuchi and H. Sato, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2012, **535**, 177.
- 55 Amsterdam Density Functional (ADF) version 2014.01 <http://www.scm.com>.
- 56 (a) A. D. Becke, *Phys. Rev. A: At., Mol., Opt. Phys.*, 1988, **38**, 3098; (b) J. P. Perdew, *Phys. Rev. B: Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.*, 1986, **33**, 8822.
- 57 D_3 GS electronic terms of HS I and III are 4A_2 and 6A_1 , respectively. No Jahn-Teller distortion⁵⁸ is foreseen for both complexes as a consequence of their not orbitally degenerate GSs.^{8c} Possible Jahn-Teller distortions associated to orbitally degenerate excited states (ES) have not been taken into account.
- 58 (a) H. A. Jahn and E. Teller, *Proc. R. Soc. London*, 1937, **A161**, 220; (b) H. A. Jahn, *Proc. R. Soc. London*, 1938, **A164**, 117. *Phys.*, 1986, **33**, 8822.
- 59 R. Hoffmann, *Solids and Surfaces: A Chemist's View of Bonding in Extended Structures*, VCH, New York, 1988.
- 60 R. S. Mulliken, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1955, **23**, 1833.
- 61 T. Ziegler and A. Rauk, *Theor. Chim. Acta* 1977, **46**, 1.
- 62 In a TM octahedral environment, the linear combinations of the six $1s^O$ AOs transform as the $a_{1g} + e_g + t_{1u}$ IRs of the O_h symmetry point group. The $O_h \rightarrow D_3$ descending symmetry implies the following correlations $a_{1g} \rightarrow a_1$; $e_g \rightarrow e$; $t_{1u} \rightarrow a_2 + e$.³⁷
- 63 (a) E. van Lenthe, E. J. Baerends and J. G. Snijders, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **99**, 4597; (b) E. van Lenthe, E. J. Baerends and J. G. Snijders, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1994, **101**, 9783; (c) E. van Lenthe, A. W. Ehlers and E. J. Baerends, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1999, **110**, 8943; (d) F. Wang and T. Ziegler, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2005, **122**, 204103.
- 64 (a) G. Fronzoni, M. Stener, P. Decleva, F. Wang, T. Ziegler, E. van Lenthe and E. J. Baerends, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2005, **416**, 56; (b) G. Fronzoni, M. Stener, P. Decleva, M. De Simone, M. Coreno, P. Franceschi, C. Furlani and K. C. Prince, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2009, **113**, 2914; (c) M. Casarin, P. Finetti, A. Vittadini, F. Wang and T. Ziegler, *J. Chem. Phys. A*, 2007, **111**, 5270; (d) M. V. Nardi, R. Verucchi, L. Pasquali, G. Fronzoni, M. Sambì, G. Mangione and M. Casarin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2015, **17**, 2001; (e) M. V. Nardi, F. Detto, L. Aversa, R. Verucchi, G. Salvati, S. Iannotta and M. Casarin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, **15**, 12864; (f) G. Mangione, S. Carlotto, M. Sambì, G. Ligorio, M. Timpel, A. Vittadini, M. V. Nardi and M. Casarin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2016, **18**, 18727; (g) G. Mangione, M. Sambì, S. Carlotto, A. Vittadini, G. Ligorio, M. Timpel, L. Pasquali, A. Giglia, M. V. Nardi and M. Casarin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2016, **18**, 24890.
- 65 E. van Lenthe and E. J. Baerends, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2003, **24**, 1142.
- 66 E. K. U. Gross and W. Kohn, *Adv. Quantum Chem.*, 1990, **21**, 255.
- 67 C. Adamo and V. Barone, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1999, **110**, 6158.
- 68 O. V. Gritsenko, P. R. T. Schipper and E. J. Baerends, *Chem Phys. Lett.*, 1999, **302**, 199.
- 69 R. van Leeuwen and E. J. Baerends, *Phys. Rev. A*, 1994, **49**, 2421.
- 70 (a) Y. Zhao and D. G. Truhlar, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2006, **125**, 194101; (b) Y. Zhao and D. G. Truhlar, *Theo. Chem. Acc.*, 2008, **120**, 215.
- 71 PBE0,⁶⁷ SAOP,⁶⁸ LB94,⁶⁹ and M06⁷⁰ numerical experiments have been carried out by using the NR BP86⁵⁶ optimized geometries.
- 72 J. H. van Lenthe, S. Faas and J. G. Snijders, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2000, **328**, 107.
- 73 (a) F. Weigend and R. Ahlrichs, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2005, **7**, 3297; (b) F. Weigend, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2006, **8**, 1057.
- 74 A detailed description of basis sets' acronyms is reported in the ORCA manual (<https://orcaforum.cec.mpg.de/>).
- 75 $L_{2,3}$ -edges $^{1/|M|}f(EE)$ distributions had been also computed by adopting the hybrid XC functional PBE0⁵⁶ but the overall agreement between theory and experiment has been found definitely better when employing the hybrid meta-GGA functional.
- 76 (a) E. J. Baerends, D. E. Ellis and P. Ros, *Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **2**, 41; (b) B. I. Dunlap, J. W. D. Connolly and J. R. Sabin, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1979, **71**, 3396; (c) C. Van Alsenoy, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 1988, **9**, 620.
- 77 V. I. Lebedev, *Zh. Vychisl. Mat. Fiz.*, 1975, **15**, 48.
- 78 D. Coster and R. D. L. Kronig, *Physica*, 1935, **2**, 13.
- 79 L. Floreano, A. Cossaro, R. Gotter, A. Verdini, G. Bavdek, F. Evangelista, A. Ruocco, A. Morgante and D. Cvetko, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2008, **112**, 10794.
- 80 T. P. Moffat, R. M. Latanision and R. R. Ruf, *Electrochimica Acta*, 1995, **40**, 1723.

- 81 J. Leveueur, G. I. N. Waterhouse, J. Kennedy, J. B. Metson and D. R. G. Mitchell, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 2011, **115**, 20978.
- 82 L. Floreano, G. Naletto, D. Cvetko, R. Gotter, M. Malvezzi, L. Marassi, A. Morgante, A. Santaniello, A. Verdini, F. Tommasini and G. Tondello, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 1999, **70**, 3855.
- 83 C. Glidewell in *Inorganic Experiments, Third Edition*, ed. D. Woolins, Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, Germany, 2010; p 109.
- 84 Unoccupied frontier orbitals may correspond to final spin orbitals – fsos – in $^{\circ}\text{K-edge}$ and $^{\text{TM}}\text{L}_{2,3}\text{-edges}$ NEXAFS transitions.
- 85 F. D. Lewis, G. D. Salvi, D. R. Kanis and M. A. Ratner, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1993, **32**, 1251.
- 86 In the adopted framework, $^{\circ}\text{t}_{2g}$ ($^{\circ}\text{t}_{2g}$) orbitals correspond to the $x^2 - y^2$ and xy (z^2) M 3d AOs, while the e_g -like ones are the xz and yz M 3d AOs. The $^{\text{TM}}\text{t}_{2g}$ AO may only interact with the a_1 linear combinations of the L-based n , and π_e orbitals. Both the localization and the relative energy position of the occupied (unoccupied) acac-based π_2 (π_4) FMO⁸⁵ concur to foresee negligible the interaction between them and the $^{\circ}\text{t}_{2g}$ AO.
- 87 The electronic configurations $a_1^1 e^2 e^0$, $a_1^1 e^2 e^1$ and $a_1^1 e^2 e^2$ are obviously reminiscent of the $t_{2g}^3 e_g^0$, $t_{2g}^3 e_g^1$ and $t_{2g}^3 e_g^2$ ones, respectively.
- 88 Throughout the paper, the MO numbering is the one corresponding to the all-electron calculations independently of the adoption of the frozen core approximation.
- 89 Spin $\uparrow$ COOPs between $^{\text{TM}^{\text{III}}}\text{t}_{2g}$ -like 3d AOs and linear combinations of (acac)₃-based π_4 FMOs, not herein reported, testifies the absence of any $^{\text{TM}^{\text{III}}}\text{t}_{2g} \rightarrow \text{L}$ backbonding.
- 90 B. Pritchard and J. Autschbach, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 8340.
- 91 The quasi degenerate (acac)₃³⁻-based 28e($\uparrow$) and 28e($\downarrow$) orbitals have the same Cr–O bonding character (see Fig 5).
- 92 (a) R. F. Nalewajski and J. Mrozek, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1994, **51**, 187; (b) R. F. Nalewajski, J. Mrozek, S. J. Formosinho and A. J. C. Varandas, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1994, **52**, 1153; (c) R. F. Nalewajski and J. Mrozek, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1996, **57**, 377; R. F. Nalewajski, J. Mrozek and G. Mazur, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1996, **74**, 1121; (d) R. F. Nalewajski, J. Mrozek and A. Michalak, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1997, **61**, 589; (e) R. F. Nalewajski, J. Mrozek and A. Michalak, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1998, **72**, 1779.
- 93 I^{NM} includes both covalent and ionic contributions.⁹²
- 94 F. L. Hirshfeld, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1977, **44**, 129.
- 95 C. Fonseca Guerra, J.-W. Handgraaf, E. J. Baerends and F. M. Bickelhaupt, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2004, **25**, 189.
- 96 In Al(acac)₃, the arrangement of the acac fragments about the 3d-electron free Al^{III} ion reproduces the one characterizing I, II, and III. BP86 calculations pertaining to the optimized Al(acac)₃ provide the following I^{NM} , $Q_{\text{Hr}}^{\text{Al}} / Q_{\text{Vor}}^{\text{Al}}$ and $Q_{\text{Hr}}^{\text{O}} / Q_{\text{Vor}}^{\text{O}}$ values: 0.49, 0.44/0.36 and -0.20/-0.20, respectively.
- 97 (a) J. W. Rabalais, *Principle of Ultraviolet Photoelectron Spectroscopy*, J. Wiley and Sons, New York, 1977; (b) R. G. Egdell and A. W. Potts in *Electronic structure and magnetism of inorganic compounds*, Chemical Society. Specialist periodical reports, 1980, **6**, 1; (c) R. G. Egdell in *Electronic structure and magnetism of inorganic compounds*, Chemical Society. Specialist periodical reports, 1982, **7**, 1.
- 98 Evans *et al.*^{28a} report in their contribution the vapour-phase He(I) PE spectra for a quite large number of β -diketonate ML_3 complexes (L = hexafluoroacac (hfa), trifluoroacac and acac; M = Al, Ga, Sc, Ti, V, Cr, Co, Mn, Fe, Ru). The Mn(hfa)₃ He(I) PE spectrum is presented by the authors (Fig. 15 of the ref. 28a), while the opposite is true for the Mn(acac)₃ one. Nevertheless, the IEs of the Mn(acac)₃ lowest lying PE features (an almost imperceptible shoulder at 7.32 eV followed by a band at 8.14 eV) are collected with data pertaining to Mn(hfa)₃ in the Table 6 of the ref. 28a.
- 99 The M(hfa)₃ PE spectra (M = Al, Cr, Fe)^{28,100} are very similar to the M(acac)₃ ones,²⁸ with the M(hfa)₃ spectral patterns uniformly blue-shifted by ~ 2 eV with respect to the M(acac)₃ ones. A rough estimate of the ¹IEs can be then obtained by referring to the Mn(hfa)₃ spectrum^{28a} and applying a red-shift of 2 eV.
- 100 D. R. Lloyd, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 868.
- 101 The wave-length (energy) of the He(I) and He(II) ionizing sources amounts to 584 (21.22 eV) and 304 Å (40.81 eV), respectively.⁹⁷
- 102 U. Gelius, in *Electron Spectroscopy*, ed. D. A. Shirley, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1972, p. 311.
- 103 A. Berndtsson, E. Basilier, U. Gelius, J. Hedman, M. Klasson, R. Nilsson, C. Nordling and S. Svensson, *Phys. Scr.*, 1975, **12**, 235.
- 104 $(\sigma_{2p}^{\text{C}})^{\text{He(II)}} / (\sigma_{2p}^{\text{C}})^{\text{He(I)}}$, $(\sigma_{2p}^{\text{O}})^{\text{He(II)}} / (\sigma_{2p}^{\text{O}})^{\text{He(I)}}$ and $(\sigma_{3d}^{\text{M}})^{\text{He(II)}} / (\sigma_{3d}^{\text{M}})^{\text{He(I)}}$ ASPCS ratios amount to 3.06×10^{-1} , 6.39×10^{-1} , and 9.25×10^{-1} (Cr), 1.56 (Mn), 1.81 (Fe).¹⁰⁵
- 105 J. J. Yeh and I. Lindau, *At. Data Nucl. Data Tables*, 1985, **32**, 1.
- 106 J. C. Slater, *Quantum Theory of Molecules and Solids. The Self-Consistent-Field for Molecules and Solids*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1974, vol. 4.
- 107 The same assignment has been proposed by Vovna *et al.*^{28f} despite the GS topmost lying orbitals they evaluated by means of Hartree-Fock-Slater discrete variational X α calculations¹⁰⁸ did not include any Cr^{III} 3d-based MOs.
- 108 (a) D. E. Ellis and G. S. Painter, *Phys. Rev. B Solid State*, 1970, **2**, 2887; (b) F. W. Averill and D. E. Ellis, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **59**, 6412; (c) E. J. Baerends, D. E. Ellis and P. Ros, *Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **2**, 41; (d) A. Rosen, D. E. Ellis, H. Adachi, H. and F. W. Averill, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1976, **65**, 3329; (e) B. Delley and D. E. Ellis, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1982, **76**, 1949.
- 109 Similar considerations hold for Ti(acac)₃ and V(acac)₃ (see Fig. 1 of the ref. 28f).
- 110 The participation of the Mn-based e_g -like and $^{\circ}\text{t}_{2g}$ orbitals to the 94a($\uparrow$) HOMO (95a($\uparrow$) LUMO)⁸⁸ amounts to 32 and 17% (33 and 23%), respectively.
- 111 In the ²TS scheme,⁶¹ the bonding energy (BE) may be written as the sum of contributions due to the steric repulsion (ΔE_{ster} , a positive quantity), in turn equal to the pure electrostatic interaction plus the Pauli repulsion, the orbital interaction (ΔE_{int} , a negative quantity) and, eventually, the so-called preparation energy and the basis set superposition error.
- 112 (a) D. R. Lloyd, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 868; (b) S. Evans, A. Hamnett and A. F. Orchard, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 1282.

- 113 The $\text{Fe}(\text{hfa})_3$ vapour-phase He(I) PE spectrum⁹⁹ is characterized by a very low intensity band at 8.28 eV that Lloyd^{112a} assigned to the ionization from the Fe^{III} e_g -like orbitals; Evans *et al.*^{112b} suggested an alternative assignment for the same PE feature: "... a shadow, excited by an additional line at 23.09 eV in the helium source, of the prominent PE band A."
- 114 F. Wang and T. Ziegler, *Mol. Phys.*, 2004, **102**, 2585.
- 115 $\text{Mn}(\text{acac})_3$ $1s^0$ -based orbitals correspond to the 6a – 11a DOMOs.
- 116 Atomic multiplets associated to the presence of four/six¹¹⁷ (five) electrons in the 3d AOs are: 5D , 3H , 3G , 3F_3 , 3D , 3P_3 , 1I , 1G_3 , 1F , 1D_3 , 1S_2 (6S , 4G , 4F , 4D , 4P , 2I , 2H , $2 \times ^2G$, $2 \times ^2F$, 2D , 2D_3 , 2P , 2S) for a total of 210 (252) microstates.¹¹⁹ The number of final state pure spin-functions that can be formed from the $2p^53d^{4/6}$ and $2p^53d^5$ configurations are 450 and 600, respectively.
- 117 "... terms arising from n (<5) d electrons outside an argon shell are the same as those arising from $10 - n$ electrons outside the same shell or, equivalently, of n holes in the completed d^{10} shell."¹¹⁸
- 118 C. J. Ballhausen, *Introduction to Ligand Field Theory*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc., New York, 1962, p. 69
- 119 The interested reader may refer to Table 4.8 of ref. 42b.
- 120 The $\Delta S = 0$ spin-selection rule is slightly released when SOC is considered. More specifically, SOC connects the terms with resultant spins S and S' , where $|S - S'| = 0, 1$.¹²¹
- 121 S. Sugano, Y. Tanabe and H. Kamimura, *Multiplets of Transition-Metal Ions in Crystals*, 1970, Academic Press, New York.
- 122 S. Carlotto, M. Sambì, F. Sedona, A. Vittadini, J. Bartolomé, F. Bartolomé and M. Casarín, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2016, **18**, 28110.
- 123 M. M. Grush, Y. Muramatsu, J. H. Underwood, E. M. Gullikson, D. L. Ederer, R. C. C. Perera, T. A. Callcott, *J. Electron. Spectrosc. Relat. Phenom.*, 1998, **92**, 22.
- 124 The inspection of Fig. 12 reveals that the $^1L_2^{-1}$ and $^3L_2^{-2}$ relative positions agree well with experimental evidences, their relative intensities are opposite to the experimental ones.